

THE GREAT NATION - WORKING PAPER

*Submitted as a Citizens' Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)*

Submitted to:

The Republic of the Philippines,
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Submitted by:

Jonelle Peter Muñoz

Date Created: September 26, 2025 to October 21, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17403156

Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in The Great Nation 2025 started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>.

Additional proposed laws will be gradually published in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #100

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Strengthening the Notarial System in the Philippines by Requiring Thumbmarks Beside Signatures on All Notarized Documents

(Individual Budget Amendments of All Elective Officials
shall also be documented and notarized with thumbmark)

- September 26, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Proposed Law #100: A Law Strengthening the Notarial System in the Philippines by Requiring Thumbmarks Beside Signatures on All Notarized Documents

All affiant/s, two witnesses, and the lawyer of the notary office must place a thumbmark on the right side of their respective signatures on every page of the notarized document.

Reason for proposing this law:

A notary office, after a person testified under oath before the Senate Blue Ribbon Committee in aid of legislation, produced another affidavit and claimed that they had not notarized the original document.

If the notary office recants its notarization, the thumbmarks of the affiant, lawyer, and two witnesses can then be authenticated by advanced technology.

This can also strengthen and improve the notarial system in the Philippines, given that there have been cases where the lawyer and the required witnesses were not present during the actual notarization.

PROPOSED LAW #101

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Members of the
Legislative Bodies, such as Senators,
Members of House of the Representatives,
City/Municipal Councilors, and Board Members,
to Explain Their Votes in a Position Paper
of at Least 500 Words

- October 2, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #101: A Law Requiring All Members of the Legislative Bodies, such as Senators, Members of House of the Representatives, City/Municipal Councilors, and Board Members, to Explain Their Votes in a Position Paper of at Least 500 Words

A law requiring Senators to explain their votes in a position paper of at least 500 words. The public may or may not be curious about the rationale behind their voting decisions.

However, public policymakers and lawmakers, as well as some concerned Filipinos, can use these position papers to further advance and strengthen public policy.

If not all legislators can explain their votes verbally, they should at least spend some time writing a position paper to justify their voting decisions.

This proposed law is also applicable to other legislative bodies such as district representatives, city/municipal councilors, and provincial board members.

PROPOSED LAW #102

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Public Disclosure of the Individual Budget Insertions and Amendments of All Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the Past Ten Years

(Also applicable to other local legislative bodies such as
city/municipal councilors and provincial board members)

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #102: A Law Requiring the Public Disclosure of the Individual Budget Insertions and Amendments of All Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the Past Ten (10) Years

There shall be a government website that itemizes all individual budget insertions and amendments made by all Senators and Members of the House of Representatives for the past ten years.

The website shall, at a minimum, include filters by Senator, Member of the House of Representatives, Name of Project, Location of Project (City and Province), Type of Project (e.g., school, hospital, road, flood control, etc.), and Status of the Project (Completed, Incomplete, Substandard, or Ghost).

This proposed law is also applicable to other local legislative bodies such as city/municipal councilors and provincial board members.

Once the government has completed the publication of data for the past ten years, it can then begin publicizing data from the 11th to 20th years in the past.

Presumption of Accountability:

To raise the standard of infrastructure projects, the burden of proof that no irregularities exist shall rest jointly on the politician, the supervising engineer, and the contractor. They share accountability to demonstrate, with verifiable evidence, that the project was executed properly and in accordance with approved standards and budgets.

The Presumption of Innocence applies to all citizens "innocent until proven guilty", as it is a fundamental human rights principle, while the Presumption of Accountability applies to all public officials in the performance of their duties and responsibilities.

PROPOSED LAW #103

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Journalists to Uphold the Highest Standards of Journalism at All Times

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #103: A Law Requiring All Journalists to Uphold the Highest Standards of Journalism at All Times

Rationale:

A journalist in the Philippines, with more than 25 years of experience, decided to publicize the list of budget amendments of ONE senator.

He disclosed that the record came from the Senate. However, HE DID NOT DISCLOSE the budget amendments and insertions of the other twenty-three (23) senators.

According to Senator Panfilo Lacson, individual budget insertions and/or amendments, whatever they may be called depending on one's perspective or definition, can amount to as much as 100 billion pesos.

And yet, this journalist, with at least 25 years of experience, chose to discuss in public only the 3 billion pesos' worth of budget amendments of one senator.

He must have seen the entire list from the Senate, and yet he decided to focus only on the budget of a single senator.

He did not discuss in detail the budgets of the other 23 senators, nor the budget amendments or insertions of all other senators in his past 25 years of journalism experience.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #104

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Creating a Special Division Under the Sandiganbayan and the Office of the Ombudsman to Focus on the Silent Transfer of Unexplained Wealth from Public Officials to Their Legal Heirs

(Exemption: Those Wealth Justified by Income Tax Returns)

- October 5, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #104: A Law Creating a Special Division Under the Sandiganbayan and the Office of the Ombudsman to Focus on the Silent Transfer of Unexplained Wealth from Public Officials to Their Legal Heirs

The competent and independent lawyers and accountants of the Special Division shall focus on the silent transfer of unexplained wealth from corrupt public officials to their legal heirs.

Rationale:

Corruption in the Philippines is so systematic and unprecedented in world history that we should not only focus on the public officials themselves but also on their legal heirs.

Important Provision:

Aside from the Certificate Authorizing Registration (CAR) from the BIR, which is a crucial requirement in transferring properties, the legal heirs of all corrupt public officials shall also receive the following:

1. An original certified copy of the first SALN of their parents or grandparents who have served as public officials;
2. The estimated amount of unexplained wealth stolen by their parents or grandparents who have served as public officials;
3. The local and national corruption rankings of their parents or grandparents, as estimated by an independent organization;
4. The estimated opportunity cost caused by the public officials' corruption (e.g., the number of Filipino children deprived of education and a better future, or the number of Filipinos who died due to poor healthcare);

5. A certified true copy of all the income tax returns (ITRs) of their parents and grandparents who have served as public officials;
6. The number of real estate properties owned before and after assuming public office (to be specified by type of property, total area in square meters, etc.).

Amendment to Existing Law:

The unexplained wealth of public officials cannot be inherited by their legal heirs unless proven through all ITRs that such wealth was accumulated in good faith.

The legal heirs of all corrupt public officials shall not inherit the wealth without attending at least a one-month seminar about the greed of their parents and grandparents, and the opportunity costs of such unimaginable greed.

PROPOSED LAW #105

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Conduct of Systematic and Transparent Localized Sandiganbayan Public Hearings Involving Public Officials and Contractors in Every City, Municipality, and Province (Prioritizing those with Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects)

- October 10, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #105: A Law Requiring the Conduct of Systematic and Transparent Localized Sandiganbayan Public Hearings Involving Public Officials and Contractor in every City, Municipality and Province

There's one President and one Vice President in the Philippines.

There are 24 Senators, 1,493 Municipal Mayors, 149 City Mayors, 82 Governors, 254 District Representatives, and 64 Party-list Representatives.

In total, there are 2,068 number of high ranking politicians in the Philippines. I exclude the board members, and city/municipal councilors for simplicity of the computation.

If, hypothetically, at least 90% of them are corrupt and have incomplete/substandard/ghost infrastructure projects, and on average it will take three months to have a final Sandiganbayan court decision,

then it would take x number of months or years to put all of the corrupt politicians in jail.

$$2,068 \times 90\% = 1,861$$

x number of months if the cases will be process on SEQUENCE or one case at a time.
One case every three months.

5,583 months or 465 years

While,

x number of months if the cases will be process SIMULTANEOUSLY using systematic and transparent Sandiganbayan Public Hearing in every city, municipality and province.

$$1,493 + 149 + 82 = 1,724 \text{ local Sandiganbayan courts}$$

3 to 6 months only since there are 1,861 high ranking public officials.

The above excludes the DPWH/LGU Engineer and the Contractor of the infrastructure project. It will take many many months before the Philippines can put all corrupt public officials in jail if done in SEQUENCE compared to SIMULTANEOUS (three to six months) if there is a local Sandiganbayan Court in every City, Municipality and Province.

Also, the computation is just a conservative estimate. The three months final court decision is too ideal in the Philippines, unless otherwise institutionalised.

The corruption in the Philippines is systemic and unprecedented in world history. We need a systemic solution.

Empower the existing constitutional bodies such as the Commission on Audit (COA), Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan. Make them highly independent, with the budget automatically allocated to them.

Hire as many lawyers and accountants as possible, in proportion to the estimated number of corrupt public officials.

Then make all hearings public, like the exact transparency in the Blue Ribbon Committee with Facebook and YouTube Live.

All local constituents are invited to every local Sandiganbayan public hearing, so the venue could be open spaces such as gymnasiums and evacuation centers.

PROPOSED LAW #106

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All Politicians, Supervising Engineers, and Contractors to Retrofit Their Respective Substandard Projects and Complete Their Incomplete and Ghost Projects Within twelve (12) Months

(Life sentence shall be imposed on any individual
who fails to complete the respective project they
signed within the prescribed 12-month period)

- October 9, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #106: A Law Requiring All Politicians, Supervising Engineers, and Contractors to Retrofit Their Respective Substandard Projects and Complete Their Incomplete and Ghost Projects Within twelve (12) Months

Proposed Penalty:

Failure to complete any incomplete, substandard, or ghost project within the next 12 months shall result in permanent disqualification from holding any public office.

Furthermore, all assets and properties, except those declared in their first Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth (SALN), shall be automatically transferred to the Republic of the Philippines.

A life sentence shall also be imposed on any individual who fails to complete the respective project they signed within the prescribed 12-month period.

Rationale:

Corruption in the Philippines is unprecedented in world history. It is like a systemic multibillion-peso money heist I once watched on Netflix, where most of the team members appear good in public but are devilish in private. They carefully plan, organize, and strategize how to steal money from poor Filipino children.

Since their crime and actions have been exposed to the public, it is reasonable to require them to complete their projects within a reasonable timeline.

This proposed law is written for Filipino children who are deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed.

PROPOSED LAW #107

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Mandatory Reporting of Unexplained Wealth by Immediate Relatives of Corrupt Public Officials and Their Conspirators or Contractors

(Prioritizing those with Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects)

- October 9, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

~~Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed~~

Proposed Law #107: Mandatory Reporting of Unexplained Wealth by Relatives of Corrupt Public Officials and their Contractors

Rationale:

When someone finds money in a public place, the natural action of a good person is to return it to the authorities. If it is proven through evidence that the person did not return the money, the authorities can file a theft case against them.

The same principle should apply to the spouse and immediate family members of politicians, contractors, or public officials.

If they know the whereabouts of unexplained wealth of their relatives who are incumbent or former politicians, public officials, or government contractors, they must report it to the authorities. Failure to do so makes them complicit.

Eating and praying daily with a theft is an insult to those Filipino children who have to work hard so that they can eat and go to school, and to those who have lost their future because of greed.

Important Provisions:

1. Scope - Applies to spouses, parents, siblings, and adult children of politicians, contractors, or public officials.

Covers unexplained wealth, assets, or financial transactions inconsistent with lawful income.

2. Duty to Report - Family members must report any unexplained wealth of their relative to the Ombudsman within 30 days of its discovery.

Knowledge of such wealth without reporting constitutes complicity in corruption. Complicity means "kasangkot".

3. Enforcement - Anti-corruption authorities shall have the power to investigate reported wealth.

Consequences for non-reporting include fines, one-month seminar, and criminal liability.

4. Purpose - To ensure that unexplained or stolen wealth is returned to the public, specially to those children deprived of education and a better future.

To hold family members accountable for knowingly concealing corruption.

To minimize corruption. If public officials, contractors, or politicians know that their family members could one day report them to the Ombudsman, they will think twice before stealing money from the poor.

Legal Basis:

Under Article 308 of the Revised Penal Code, theft is committed by anyone who, having found lost property, fails to deliver it to the local authorities or its owner. This provision establishes an obligation for finders to make reasonable efforts to return lost property.

"Maraming kabataan ang napipilitang mag-dropout sa paaralan dahil sa kakulangan ng scholarship at maayos na edukasyon. Kung pagkatapos ay may daang milyon na unexplained wealth ang asawa, kapatid, nanay, tatay, lolo, o lola mo, hindi mo ba ito irereport sa awtoridad para matulungan ang kapwa mo Pilipino?"

PROPOSED LAW #108

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring the Registry of Deeds and
the Land Registration Authority to
Submit to the Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan
All Unexplained Real Estate Properties
of All Public Officials and Contractors
Involved in Substandard, Incomplete or Ghost Projects

- October 10, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #108: A Law Requiring the Registry of Deeds and Land Registration Authority to Submit to the Ombudsman All Unexplained Real Estate Properties of all Corrupt Public Officials and Their Contractors

This proposed law prioritizes those who have unreasonable increase in real estate properties within a short period of time, particularly within the past five to ten years.

Greedy politicians, public officials, and contractors involved in substandard, incomplete and ghost infrastructure projects shall automatically be included in the list.

Once proven to be unexplained wealth by verifiable evidence, those real estate properties shall be returned to the Republic of the Philippines to fund the construction of schools and provide scholarships for Filipino children.

This can be a good alternative to SALN publications, serving as a database of unexplained wealth directly from the Registry of Deeds and LRA.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #109

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Imposing a Penalty of Life Imprisonment and Perpetual Disqualification from Public Office on Those Public Officials Who Have Unexplained Wealth of at Least Ten (10) Million Pesos for Three (3) Consecutive Years

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #109: A Law Imposing a Penalty of Life Imprisonment and Perpetual Disqualification from Public Office on Those Public Officials Who Have Unexplained Wealth of at Least Ten (10) Million Pesos for Three (3) Consecutive Years

Important Provision:

Exceptions are those declared in the first SALN, or any wealth justifiable with ITR.

10 Million can be changed to any amount as maybe deemed necessary threshold by highly independent experts.

Within three years after the passage of this law, the public officials have the option to transfer all their unexplained wealth to the Republic of the Philippines, specifically to build schools at a reasonable cost.

If after the three (3) years period, they still do not return their unexplained wealth to the poor Filipino children through the building of schools and providing scholarships, then the penalty of life imprisonment and perpetual disqualification shall be final.

Additionally, all their legal heirs up to the third generation cannot inherit any unexplained wealth unless proven by their parent's and grandparent's ITR.

10 Million is my proposed threshold, it could be lower or higher to be finalized by the future Congress.

I mean, if you have 10 Million in your bank account, why do you need an excess of that? Those are just numbers, unless used for the greater good.

10 Million is a reasonable amount of money to live a comfortable and happy life in the retirement period. Or maybe 5 Million or lower, depending on how frugal a person can be.

Any excess of 10 Million will be an opportunity of a lifetime to many Filipino children.

This proposed law will be amended and completed in the future. I'm optimistic that a wise Filipino president will prioritize this piece of legislation in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #110

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All DPWH and LGU Engineers
to Inspect and Retrofit (When Necessary)
All Public Infrastructure Buildings,
Especially Schools, Which Are Considered
a Second Home by Millions of Filipino Children
(With Automatic Local Budget Allocation Provision)

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #110: A Law Requiring All DPWH and LGU Engineers to Inspect and Retrofit (if needed) All Public Infrastructure Buildings, especially Schools, which are considered a second home by millions of Filipino children.

Proposed Penalty: For each child casualty in a specific locality, the highest local DPWH and LGU Engineer shall be the most accountable.

Their one-month salary shall automatically be donated to the immediate family members of the child.

In case of at least five (5) casualties due to poor building construction and inspection, those signatories of the public infrastructure project shall be disallowed to run for public office for six (6) years.

If it is proven by verifiable evidence that the infrastructure projects that caused five (5) casualties are due to corruption or kickbacks, then the politician and DPWH/LGU Engineer involved shall be perpetually disqualified from holding public office.

Their one-month salary shall automatically be donated to the family members of each casualty.

Ideally, there must be at least one DPWH/LGU Engineer accountable for all schools in every three to five barangays. This shall be their additional duty and responsibility, as to be amended in the Local Government Code of 1991.

All Local Chief Executives, such as Mayors and Governors, shall be required to automatically appropriate local budgets once the LGU/DPWH Engineer deems it necessary to retrofit a school building.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

PROPOSED LAW #111

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

A Law Requiring All CoA Auditors or Their Designated Spokesperson to Explain All Their Individual Audit Findings to the Public via Facebook or YouTube Live

- October 12, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Law #111: A Law Requiring All CoA Auditors or Their Designated Spokesperson to Explain All their Individual Audit Findings to the Public via Facebook or YouTube Live.

"Justice delayed is justice denied." The public can't wait for one year or more, or worst, 10 years for a final Sandiganbayan court ruling. The politician, contractor, or public official involved will keep stealing again every year if there is no final ruling within the first year.

Exception:

If the irregularities involve at least Php 50 million, the CoA auditors or their designated spokesperson shall be required to explain it to the public via Facebook or YouTube Live within three (3) months.

The Php 50 million limit can be changed to Php 25 million or any amount not lower than Php 500,000.

Important Provisions:

Thirty (30) days after the CoA auditors or their designated spokesperson make a live Facebook or YouTube video, the involved politicians, contractors, or engineers shall be required to explain their innocence with verifiable evidence to the public via Facebook or YouTube Live.

According to the 1987 Constitution, "Public office is a public trust. Public officers and employees must, at all times, be accountable to the people, serve them with utmost responsibility, integrity, loyalty, and efficiency; act with patriotism and justice, and lead modest lives."

All COA auditors are accountable to the people, not to politicians. Your reports must be explained and be known to the public. You spend the whole year gathering evidence, inspecting properties, services, and goods, and writing the final audit report, only to wait by luck or by chance, to see whether it will be forwarded by the Ombudsman to the Sandiganbayan?

To all CoA auditors, "If you believe there is an anomaly, you can explain it to the public tomorrow morning or afternoon. Thank you in advance."

Greedy public officials and/or contractors who often steal money from poor Filipino children will think twice before doing it again, because independent CoA auditors will be required by this law to explain their wrongdoings to the public.

This proposed law will be amended and completed with proper sections. I'm optimistic that a wise Filipino president will prioritize this piece of legislation in the future.

Proposed Law #112: A Law Publicizing the First Declared SALN and the Current SALN in a Centralised Government Website so the Citizen Can Save Time in Requesting, Traveling and Getting Those Public Records.

All SALN are notarised, so by default they become a public domain.

Proposed Law #113: A Law Publicizing the Itemized Breakdown of Unprogrammed Funds in the Past Ten (10) Years

These unprogrammed funds could have fixed the school backlogs that will take thirty (30) years to be filled.

It can also serve as a REAL FINANCIAL LIFELINE for those Filipino college students who are forced to dropout school due to the lack of scholarships.

Proposed Law #114: A Law Requiring All Members of Legislative Bodies, such as Senators and Congressmen, to Document, Publish, and Notarize Accomplishment and Status Reports, Together with the Corresponding Financial Statements for All Their Respective Projects

Rationale:

Legislators who propose, amend, or insert budgets into the General Appropriations Act (GAA) must be fully accountable for the projects funded under their initiatives, in coordination with the engineers and contractors involved.

Important Provision:

No member of any legislative body can propose, amend, or insert any budget item into the General Appropriations Act (GAA) if they have not submitted an Accomplishment and Status Report, together with the corresponding financial statement of all their respective projects from the previous year.

Three (3) years after the passage of this law, all former members of the legislative bodies of the Philippines shall be required to prepare, publish, and notarize the above-mentioned documents covering the duration of their public service.

Penalty:

Failure to comply with this law shall result in disqualification from holding any public office for a period of six (6) years. No individual budget amendments/insertion without above-mentioned documents of the previous year.

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

Proposed Law #115: A Law Requiring the Office of the Ombudsman and the Sandiganbayan to Publish Accomplishment Report Every Month, Quarter, and Year on Their Official Website and Facebook Page.

Important Provisions:

The accomplishment report MUST include the following details:

1. The number of complaints received by the Office of the Ombudsman every month, every quarter, and every year, as well as the performance of each lawyer in the past ten years.

I mean, do we really have a working Ombudsman? We would not be in this unprecedented level of corruption in world history if only their lawyers or prosecutors had done their job in the past ten years.

2. The status of each complaint, including the date it was received and the date a final decision was made.

3. A NOTARISED WRITTEN EXPLANATION from the lawyer under the Office of the Ombudsman who handled each specific complaint. This explanation must include the reason why the case was dismissed or not, the amount involved, and any other important information surrounding the complaint.

The public deserves to know if we truly have an independent constitutional body that does its job. We also need to know exactly which lawyers under the Office of the Ombudsman are responsible for dismissing specific complaints.

If the complaint is dismissed, the complainant can publicize his or her written complaint. Just redact personal information due to privacy law.

I think that the written complaint is a notarized document, so by default, it is a public document. If only we had an FOI Law, those documents would have been public by default, reducing the time needed for requesting, traveling, and receiving a copy.

Penalty:

A lawyer who dismisses a complaint twice that should have been forwarded to the Sandiganbayan shall be perpetually disqualified from holding any public office.

Due process against this lawyer shall be observed and conducted in a regular court.

Separability Clause: If any part of this law is declared unconstitutional, the remaining provisions shall remain in full force and effect.

This proposed law will be amended in the future with complete sections. This is just the core idea, like the past proposed laws.

Proposed Executive Order

MANDATING ALL ELECTIVE AND HIGH-RANKING PUBLIC OFFICIALS TO MAINTAIN, PUBLICIZE, AND NOTARIZE A LEDGER OF ALL CONTRACTS AND PUBLIC DOCUMENTS THEY SIGNED

PROPOSED EXECUTIVE ORDER NO. ____

MANDATING ALL ELECTIVE AND HIGH-RANKING PUBLIC OFFICIALS TO MAINTAIN, PUBLICIZE, AND NOTARIZE A LEDGER OF ALL CONTRACTS AND PUBLIC DOCUMENTS THEY SIGNED

Date Proposed: October 17, 2025

WHEREAS, transparency and accountability are foundational principles of good governance and essential to maintaining public trust in government institutions;

WHEREAS, elective officials and high-ranking officials exercise authority over public funds, contracts, and documents that significantly affect the welfare of the citizens;

WHEREAS, it is necessary to ensure that all government transactions and contracts are open to public scrutiny and that the identity of all signatories to such documents is verifiable and documented;

NOW, THEREFORE, I, _____, President of the Republic of the Philippines, by virtue of the powers vested in me by the Constitution and existing laws, do hereby order the following:

SECTION 1. Coverage. This Order shall apply to all elective officials and high-ranking public officials with a monthly salary grade or compensation exceeding Eighty Thousand Pesos (Php 80,000), including but not limited to:

- The President and Vice President of the Republic;
- Members of the Cabinet, Department Secretaries, and Undersecretaries;
- Senators and Members of the House of Representatives; and
- Governors and Mayors of provinces, cities, and municipalities.

SECTION 2. The Official Ledger of Signed Documents. Every covered official shall maintain, publicize, and notarize a Ledger of Contracts and Public Documents Signed (hereinafter referred to as the Ledger), to be updated and made public monthly.

The Ledger shall include the following details for each document or contract signed:

1. Title or Name of the Document or Contract;
2. Initials of All Other Signatories and the last four (4) digits of their plantilla number or birth number if private individual (e.g., Jonelle Peter Muñoz – JPM1234 or JPM12051990);
3. Amount Involved in the contract or document;
4. Notarization Details (e.g., Name of Lawyer, Date of Notarization and Notarial Register Entries such as Doc. No., Page No., Book No. and Series of ____); and
5. Brief Description of the purpose or scope of the document (e.g., “Construction of a four-storey public school building at [exact address]”). The description should be approximately 50 to 100 words.

SECTION 3. Publication Requirement. Each covered official shall publish their Ledger every month on their official government social media account or public website (e.g., official Facebook page), ensuring that the information is accessible to the public.

SECTION 4. Notarization and Record Retention. The Ledger shall be notarized at least once every quarter and may be stored or uploaded to an immutable digital platform for public record and verification.

All Ledgers and related documents shall be maintained for a minimum of ten (10) years, consistent with the document retention requirements of the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) to all taxpayers.

SECTION 5. Prioritization of High-Value Contracts. High Priority: All contracts and documents involving an amount exceeding **Php** 500,000 shall be promptly included in the Ledger.

Mandatory Disclosure: All contracts and documents involving an amount exceeding **Php** 5,000,000 are required to be recorded, published, and notarized in accordance with this Order.

SECTION 6. Independent Monitoring. Independent organizations, auditors, civil society groups, and qualified experts shall be allowed to review, verify, and audit the published Ledgers to promote transparency and detect possible misuse of public funds.

SECTION 7. Penalties and Automatic Suspension. Failure by any covered official to maintain, notarize, or publicize their Ledger in accordance with this Order shall result in automatic suspension from office, subject to administrative and legal proceedings under existing laws and regulations.

SECTION 8. Retroactive Compliance. Within three (3) years from the effectivity of this Order, all covered officials shall compile, notarize, and publicize all documents and contracts they have signed during their term of service.

SECTION 9. Local Ordinance. Local Government Units (LGUs) are required to adopt this measure through local ordinances to strengthen transparency and accountability at the municipal, city, and provincial levels.

SECTION 10. Effectivity. This Presidential Order shall take effect immediately upon issuance and shall remain in force unless amended, repealed, or superseded by law.

DONE, in the City of Manila, this ___ day of _____, in the Year of Our Lord Two Thousand and Twenty-Five.

BY THE PRESIDENT:

President of the Republic of the Philippines

PROPOSED BY:

JONELLE PETER C. MUÑOZ

Citizen of the Republic of the Philippines

Date Proposed: October 17, 2025

Submitted as a Citizen's Proposal under the Right to Petition the Government

(Article III, Section 4 of 1987 Constitution)

Proposed to **The Republic of the Philippines**,
through the Senate and House of Representatives

Proposed Law #117: A Law Setting Minimum Good Governance Membership Requirements for Local Chief Executives such as Mayor and Governor

1. Must have a Freedom of Information Ordinance and an Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance. (The FOI Ordinance should be of the same quality as that of Pasig City, which includes a penalty clause. The Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance is yet to be created.)
2. Must have a public SALN from the first year of being a public official up to the present (if incumbent).
3. Must have a bank secrecy waiver. (Available upon request by the Ombudsman. Making it public is optional, as it can be used politically.)
4. Must have a city, municipality or province with adequate schools proportionate to the number of Out-of-School Youth and Adults (OSYA). (Proposed Law #2 last year)
5. Must have a public ledger of all contracts or documents signed in the conduct of duties and responsibilities. (see Proposed Law #116 or Proposed EO published on October 17)
6. Must have an ordinance requiring all elective officials to work full-time, from 8 am to 5 pm five days a week, like ordinary employees. (Full Time Ordinance)
7. Must have a transparent local website, similar to that of Singapore, with all legislative uploaded and publicized, in addition to those already required by law to be posted in public places.
8. Must have signed, publicized and notarized an affidavit stating that all wealth in excess of Php 5 million shall be donated to the education sector, especially for building schools and providing scholarships to Filipino children. (Exemption: Those wealth in first SALN, or wealth justifiable by ITR)
9. Must conduct at least a two-hour public forum with his or her constituents once a month (at least two hours per week for better public participation).
10. Must have a notarized transcript of all meetings related to his or her duties and responsibilities, to assess whether the decisions are made in the best interest of the people and the greater good.

This list and proposed law will be updated in the future.

It may also serve as a minimum requirement to join a strong political party in the Philippines.

Proposed Law #118: A Law to Address the School Backlogs Across the Entire Philippines

Important Provisions:

1. Require the Department of Public Works and Highways to publicize the school backlog in every city, municipality, and province.
2. The data must cover school backlogs from the past ten (10) to twenty (20) years.
3. The Local Chief Executives, such as mayors and governors, must work together with their respective DPWH regional, provincial, and district offices to address these backlogs.
4. Remove the highest-ranking regional, provincial, or district DPWH engineer if they fail to fix the backlog in the next twelve (12) months.
5. Require these highest ranking local DPWH engineer or their designated spokesperson to publicly explain why there is a significant backlog in their jurisdiction.
6. They must explain what their priorities were during the past five (5) to ten (10) years, and where their empathy and compassion lie for the Filipino children who had to stop schooling because they walk more than an hour or two each day.
7. They must also itemize how they spent their budget during the past ten (10) years, including:
 1. The contracts they signed,
 2. The amounts involved, and
 3. Whether those projects were more important than building adequate schools for the Filipino children.
8. Require them to maintain a public disclosure ledger. (See Proposed Law #116)

This proposed law will be amended in the future.

Proposed Law #119: A Law Requiring All Local Chief Executives and Highest Local DPWH Official to Publicize, Notarize and Explain in Public All Documents They Signed.

A simple solution to gradually eradicate systemic corruption at the local level in the next three years.

LCE means Mayor and Governor.

Important Provision: All public documents that are not publicized and notarized shall be considered void and not binding.

If they cannot explain the documents in public, they can hire an official spokesperson to speak on their behalf.

There shall be a local FB page or group for public documents signed and notarised by the LCE and highest local DPWH official.

We can standardize the name of the FB Page/Group such as:

Name of LGU + Public Documents

Example:

Laguna Province Public Documents

Cabuyao City Public Documents

So that it would be easy for the citizens to find their respective public contracts.

A website can be created with a better filter by the type of public document. (e.g. filter by contracts, resolutions, MOA, MOU, ordinance, etc.)

All citizens pay tax. And those public documents would not be possible without our collective contribution as the citizens of the Republic.

This is just the core idea, and will be amended in the future.

Applicable not just at the local level and DPWH, but also to other branches of governments and departments such as the Department of Health, Department of Education, Department of Information and Technology, etc.

PROPOSED TRANSPARENCY DOCTRINE

Submitted as a Citizen's Legislative Proposal under the
Right to Petition the Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)

All documents signed by elective officials
and high-ranking officials must be publicized,
notarized, and explained to the public.

Enhanced Principle of Immutability

Any public document that is not publicized, notarized, and
explained to the public shall be considered
VOID AND NOT BINDING, as if the document does not exist.

- October 20, 2025 -

Proposed to

The Republic of the Philippines
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Written for the Filipino children deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed

Proposed Transparency Doctrine

This doctrine strengthens the traditional principle of immutability by asserting that no public document, such as contracts, can possess legal force unless it is made transparent, notarized, verified, and understood by the public.

Date introduced to the humanity: October 20 to 21, 2025

Under this proposed doctrine:

1. All elective officials and high-ranking officials are required to notarize and explain to the public through their designated spokesperson all public documents, such as contracts, agreements, or any official acts involving the use of public resources.
2. There must be one designated spokesperson, ideally a lawyer or reputable journalist with at least three (3) years of professional experience to explain all public documents signed. An individual with a background in contract law is preferred.

The spokesperson or journalist shall work full-time, eight hours per day, five (5) days per week, like an ordinary employee, to explain all public documents signed by all elective officials and high-ranking officials.

Priority of having a designated spokesperson:

1. Elective Local Chief Executives, such as Mayors and Governors
2. Department Secretaries and the highest Regional, Division, or District Heads.
3. The President of the Philippines

This proposed doctrine represents only the core principle and will be improved in the future. The President may adopt the above-mentioned principle as an Executive Order, as early as tomorrow morning or the next day.